

Kinetics of Reaction Between Iodoacetate and Thiosulphate Ions : Part II

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The influences of electrolytes and non electrolytes on the rate constant of the reaction between iodoacetate and thiosulphate ions have been investigated. The changes in the rate constant of the reaction are different in presence of different electrolytes or non electrolytes. The parameter "d" i.e., the distance of closest approach of the reactant ions is calculated using Scatchard equation and is found 5.31 Å. The mechanism of the reaction has been proposed.

It was shown in a previous communication¹ from this laboratory that the variation of the kinetic activity factor with total ionic strength in the reaction between iodoacetate and thiosulphate ions is in good agreement with Bronsted-Debye² equation. The total ionic strength can also be changed by adding varying quantities of the different neutral salts. The present work was therefore undertaken with a view to investigate whether the increase in ionic strength could increase the rate constant of the reaction in the same magnitude as the increase in rate constant was observed when the ionic strength was changed by variation in the concentration of electrolytes. The salts used for the purpose were nitrates of potassium and lanthanum.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either B.D.H. Analytical reagents or E Mercks guaranteed quality. The solutions were prepared in conductivity water by dissolving weighed quantities of salts. The experiment was conducted in electrically operated thermostat maintained at $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The solutions of the reactants and electrolytes were kept in the thermostat for one hour and then mixed and aliquots were titrated against standard iodine solution. In Table I the strengths of reactants and electrolyte contained in the reaction mixture are given with the corresponding values of the rate constants.

From Table I it is clear that the effect of adding electrolytes to the reaction mixture, the rate constant

increases with increasing total ionic strength but the increase in the rate constant is more pronounced in presence of lanthanum nitrate than potassium nitrate. Hence it is concluded that besides the effect of increase of total ionic strength the electrolytes exhibit their specific influences on rate constant of the reaction.

The non electrolytes used under investigations were urea sugar, ethanol and dioxane. Dioxane was purified following the method described by La Mer and coworker³. The solutions of non electrolyte of required strengths were prepared in conductivity water and then exact quantities of sodium iodoacetate and sodium thiosulphate were dissolved in the different flasks containing the known volumes of mixed solvents. The same procedure as described above was followed and rate constants at different ionic strengths in the mixed solvents having different dielectric constants have been calculated.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained are given in Table 2 from the values of $\log k$ corresponding to under root of ionic strength, the log of rate constant at zero ionic strength and values of $\frac{d \log k}{d\sqrt{\mu}}$ determined for different mixed solvents. Table 3 contains the theoretical and observed value of $\frac{d \log k}{d\sqrt{\mu}}$ and the values of $\log k$ at zero ionic strength for the different mixed solvents.

TABLE I—RATE CONSTANT IN PRESENCE OF ELECTROLYTE AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS

Sodium Iodoacetate	Sodium Thiosulphate	Potassium Nitrate	Lanthanum Nitrate	Total ionic strength	Rate constant k in litre mole ⁻¹ /min ⁻¹
0.002M	0.001M	0.003M	—	0.008M	0.443
0.002 "	0.001 "	0.005 "	—	0.010 "	0.464
0.002 "	0.001 "	0.015 "	—	0.020 "	0.511
0.002 "	0.001 "	—	0.0005M	0.008 "	0.721
0.002 "	0.001 "	—	0.0008 "	0.010 "	0.905
0.002 "	0.001 "	—	0.0025 "	0.020 "	1.120

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANT, k IN LITRE MOLE⁻¹ MIN⁻¹ IN DIFFERENT MIXED SOLVENTS AT 20°

Solvent used	Dielectric constant	Ionic strength 0.0025 M	Strength 0.005 M	0.010 M	0.020 M
3 M urea in water	86.1	0.426	0.457	0.514	0.562
Pure water	80	0.352	0.304	0.443	0.500
Sucrose 20% by wt.	74	0.284	0.316	0.365	0.398
Dioxane 10% by vol.	71	0.258	0.288	0.333	0.359
Sucrose 30% by wt.	67	0.199	0.251	0.260	0.324
Dioxane 20% by vol.	62.3	0.190	0.214	0.251	0.269
Ethanol 40% by vol.	57.3	0.174	0.195	0.235	0.251
Dioxan 30% by vol.	53.3	0.162	0.186	0.224	0.241
Sucrose 50% by wt	49	0.166	0.191	0.235	0.251

 TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANT, k IN LITRE/MOLE/MIN AT $\mu=0$

Dielectric Constant D	$\frac{1000}{D}$	Theoretical $\frac{1 \log k}{d\sqrt{\mu}}$	Observed $\frac{d \log k}{d\sqrt{\mu}}$	$1 + \log k_{\mu=0}$
86.1	11.6	1.85	1.88	0.523
80.0	12.5	2.00	2.00	0.446
74.0	13.5	2.16	2.16	0.346
71.0	14.0	2.235	2.22	0.301
67.0	14.9	2.38	2.36	0.180
62.3	16.0	2.573	2.4	0.160
57.3	17.3	2.77	2.61	0.110
53.3	18.7	3.93	2.8	0.070
49.0	20.4	4.106	3.01	0.070

From Table 2 it is clear that the rate constant of the reaction between iodoacetate and thiosulphate decrease with decrease of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the mixed solvents. The values of dielectric constant of mixed solvents are taken from book of physico-chemical constants⁴. From

Table 2 the values of $\frac{d \log k}{d\sqrt{\mu}}$ are calculated and shown

in Table 3. Bronsted theory is quantitatively applicable below ionic strength = 0.01 M and above the dielectric constant 67. Below dielectric constant 67 Bronsted theory could predict the course of the reaction qualitatively. The rate constants at zero ionic strength in the mixed solvents of different dielectric constants are plotted against inverse of dielectric constants of mixed solvents (Fig. 1). Scatchard⁵ theory is applicable above the dielectric constant 67. The rate constant at zero ionic strength in the mixed solvents having dielectric constant somewhat in the neighbourhood of 50 is almost unaffected by the change in the dielectric constant. The value of $\log k$ at zero ionic strength and infinite dielectric constant is obtained by extrapolating. The line relating $\log k$ and inverse of dielectric constant to $1/D = 0$. The value of $\log k^{\circ}$ at $1/D = 0$ is 0.61 litre mole⁻¹min⁻¹. Scatchard equation is used to calculate the distance of closest approach of the reactant ions.

$$\log k^{\circ} = \log k^{0*} - \frac{NZ_A Z_B e^2}{2.3 RDTd}$$

or

$$1.453 = 0.61 - \frac{6.06 \times 10^{23} \times 1 \times 2 \times (4.803 \times 10^{-10})^2}{2.303 \times 8.34 \times 10^7 \times 293.2 \times 80d}$$

Hence $d = 5.31 \text{ \AA}$.

The reaction between iodoacetate and thiosulphate is of second order being first order with respect to each reactant¹. The reaction rate increases with increase in ionic strength indicates that the reaction takes place between the ions of same sign. This has been confirmed by the fact that the rate of reaction decreases when the dielectric constant of the medium, in which reaction is taking place, is decreased. Scatchard equation enables to calculate the distance of closest approach of the reactant ions. The iodine atom of the iodoacetate ion is replaced by the 'thiosulphate' ion is confirmed by the fact that after the completion of the reaction, in the reaction mixture the amount of iodide ion, produced is equivalent to the amount of decrease in the thiosulphate ion concentration. Hence the SN_2 mechanism for the reaction has been suggested.

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = k[\text{I CH}_2\text{COO}^-][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]$$

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